

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

THE NEW EU CYBERSECURITY STRATEGY AND INTERAGENCY POLICIES EVOLVEMENTS

Author: Sabrina Medeiros

POLICY STATEMENT

Discussions on the cybersecurity domain touch on some principles undergoing accelerated transformation, both from state renewal and business arena. This transformation points to a significant movement in the communication channels which are little subject to external control since the very nature of these relations escapes the institutional ingredients available from states and international regimes. If the way interactions take place inhibits surveillance, ties' intensification presents a moral regulatory demand that manifests itself as a relevant component of the global system's stability. The European Union launched in Dec 2020 its new EU Cybersecurity Strategy (1), and the challenges it is posed to deal with are only achievable through overlapping policies with a comprehensive and across borders feasible framework.

BACKGROUND

The biggest dilemma regarding the acceleration of dynamics in the cyber domain seems to be moral or how state and non-state agents will promote and submit themselves to the cyber diomains's rules. On the other hand, the cyber domain has unique materiality because its impacts are directed at the visible and non-visible structures in progress.

Thus, the cyber domain structures can be organized as those connected to: data privacy and cyber violence, institutional and infrastructure security; security of supply chains, networks of financial and material flows, and inter-agency relationships, including intelligence systems. When observing this typology, we can notice that the affected dimensions impact the civil world, the states, and their relations. But, notably, the relationships among agents, whether from the civilian world or state and interstate structures, are the most critical because their nature is essentially changeable and uncertain. Although structures are the target of destabilizing actions in the cyber domain or via cyber-systems, less visible structures can cause more damage, and those are responsible for the various connections under development.

The debate that arises is between attempts to transform the cyber domain into a morally safer system, which qualifies for multistakeholderism, and the reactions endowed with attempts to police the borders of this cyber domain based on standards of sovereignty (2). The main reason for the low effectiveness of a broad effort at sovereignty is in the existing and invisible nodes of the cyber domain, full of partitions with little visibility and significant interdependence. It does not seem reasonable in the long run that we should be able, in isolation, to create motivations for national agents to occupy these spaces without great insecurity and poor viability. For this reason, the cyber world is composed mainly of binding and non-binding agreements, given that the repercussions are more significant on the technical-operative side of these commitments than on their moral and more strategic side.

FINDINGS

The commitment to observe and work through the different levels of intra-state and inter-state relations seems to be the greatest challenge for building policies in benefit of the cyber-regulation scene. The systematic observation of good practices shows that the initiatives' strategic character has advanced due to experiments in the more practical field from the bottom side of the cybersecurity domain, with the possibility of bringing the various stakeholders to the table where public policies are created. The latest, most successful policies had significant support from the state and were heavily influenced by external directives, mostly created by regimes such as the European Union and under the UN bodies (3).

The European Union Budapest Convention and Evidence of Crime (2020), as part of the Treaty 185 (Convention on Cybercrime, 2001, into force since 2004), offers a chance for a comprehensive policy dedicated to promoting national legislation in alliance with international cooperation frameworks. Together with the Paris Call principles (2018), it permits the evolvment of the ITU Global cybersecurity agenda (2007), creating moral pillars to wrap-up relations among actors. Those moral pillars add to parties involved practical ways to organize and develop themselves accordingly, once they can be part of a permanent instrumental network of both state and private stakeholders that can be under priority. But still, there are challenges to uphold national capabilities in dealing with it, as to introduce actors out of the consolidated regimes.

The invitation to cooperate signalize that the regime spectrum is trying to cover those faces of the problem, which are both inside and outside the EU. It is still missing the way external actors will be able to add to the commitment, if so, as Benin, Brazil, Burkina Faso, Guatemala, Niger, Nigeria, South Africa, and Tunisia, which are also in the list of countries that did not ratify even the 2004 agreement on Cybersecurity (4).

On the other side, the EU Cybersecurity Strategy cover, not the moral dimensions or the core values to the discussion, but the standards in which the EU members can manifest them, with their eyes on the implications outside of the EU. A toolbox for mitigating comes together with the recommendations which standardize and guarantees those parameters that are affected and affect the moral dimension of agents below the system structure.

CONCLUSIONS

The Budapest Convention seems to aggregate some of the central values to achieve security in the cyber scene, at least, at a better level than before. Multistakeholderism was treated in another discussion level; it seems to be possible to manage the various layers of representation, without which it is not reasonable to achieve security. This will be an essential asset to the new EU Cybersecurity Strategy, which is dedicated to ensuring resilience and capabilities development, recognizing connections between internal and external security. The national level seems to be the first step to integrate the various layers, which are also to be guaranteed in the municipal or districts bodies.

SUGGESTIONS

As to deal with overlapping layers and to strengthen synergies in the benefit of interagency relations (5), there are some possible actions to be part of the coordinated processes, once dedicated funds are both military and civilian-based:

- Multi-agent exercises and military-civilian Collaboration exercises.
- Private-public interface schemes development.
- Data managerial collaborative forums.
- Research and training.
- Social responsibility and human rights in the cyber domain (6).
- Foreign relations robustness of the technical bodies and entities.

Challenges that are still to be faced in relation to external and internal security integration:

- Border Security and migration crisis as part of the efforts related.
- Federal + federative institutions (diplomacy and paradiplomacy) developments to deal with international threats such as trafficking, smuggling or poly-criminality (7).
- Private/public initiatives and regime coordination by those initiatives.
- International stakeholders and mixed interferences (vulnerabilities amplified in the same pace networks are intensified).

REFERENCES

- (1) New European Union Cybersecurity Strategy (2020). In: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_20_2391 Accessed 25DEC2020
- (2) See: Stadnik, I. (2017). What is an international cybersecurity regime and how we can achieve it. *Masaryk UJL & Tech.*, 11, 129.
- (3) See also: Štililis, D., Rotomskis, I., Laurinaitis, M., Nadvynychnyy, S., & Khorunzhak, N. (2020). National Cyber Security Strategies: Management, Unification and Assessment. <https://repository.mruni.eu/bitstream/handle/007/17022/1431-Article%20Text-25466-2-10-20200908.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y> Accessed 25DEC2020
- (4) European Union (2020). Chart of signatures and ratifications of Treaty 185 - https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/185/signatures?p_auth=DOzYeqZn Accessed 25DEC2020
- (5) See also: Ayres & Medeiros (2020). Policy Papers – Konrad Adenauer Forte de Copacabana 2020 - Digital Geopolitics and Information Security: multidimensional cybersecurity policy framework. In: <https://www.kas.de/documents/265553/265602/Policy+Papers+-+Forte+de+Copacabana+2020.pdf/ea8fd34c-5909-22fa-56d6-ace207516b14?version=1.0&t=1600095045391> Accessed 25DEC2020
- (6) See also: García Segura L.A. (2020) European Cybersecurity: Future Challenges from a Human Rights Perspective. In: Ramírez J., Biziewski J. (eds) Security and Defence in Europe. Advanced Sciences and Technologies for Security Applications. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-12293-5_3
- (7) Kuchalskis, K. (2020). Organised Crime: New Challenges and Response. *European Law Enforcement Research Bulletin*, tbc-tbc. <http://91.82.159.234/index.php/bulletin/article/view/424/321> Accessed 25DEC2020